

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE WITH SOCIAL CAPITAL AND JOB BURNOUT OF EMPLOYEES OF THE MINISTRY OF SPORTS AND YOUTH OF IRAN

Mohammad Hami^{1*}, Fahimeh Mohammad Hassan²

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Sports Management, Islamic Azad University, Sari Branch, Sari, Iran, email: mohammadhami@yahoo.com

² Assistant Professor in Sports Management, Sport Sciences research Institute of Iran, email: f.mohammadhassan@gmail.com

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

The purpose of the present research is to study the relationship between organizational culture with social capital and job burnout of employees of the ministry of sports and youth of Iran. The research is an applied research in terms of purpose, and descriptive-correlation in terms of method. The research population was including of all the employees of the ministry of sports and youth of Iran (N=950). Using the sampling table of Krejcie & Morgan 274 people were randomly selected as statistical sample. Based on this sample, 258 questionnaires were collected. The questionnaires used in this research were the standard organizational culture questionnaire of Denison et al (1999), job burnout by Hazel and Maslach (1977), social capital by Nahapiet and Ghoshal's (1998), and the validity of the questionnaire was confirmed by experts (10 people). To determine the reliability, the questionnaire was distributed among 15 people from the statistical population. This value was based on the data obtained through Cronbach's alpha equal to $\alpha = 0.79$ for the organizational culture questionnaire, job burnout $\alpha = 0.8$, social capital $\alpha = 0.8$, which indicated the high reliability of the questionnaire. In order to inferential analysis of findings and hypothesis testing, Kolmogorov Smirnov statistical models, one sample t test, analysis of variance, univariate and multiple regression, Pearson correlation coefficient and Sobel test were performed in SPSS version 25. There was a significant relationship between organizational culture and social capital of the employees ($p=0.001$, $r=0.519$). But there was no significant relationship between organizational culture and job burnout ($r=-0.235$, $p=0.228$). There was a significant and direct relationship between the components of organizational culture and the social capital of the employees of the ministry. There was no relationship between organizational culture components and job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth employees. Also, the significant effect of organizational culture on the social capital of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth was confirmed ($p=0.001$, $t=3.76$). However, the significant effect of organizational culture on job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth employees was not confirmed ($p=0.378$, $t=0.9$). In addition, organizational culture had a significant mediating effect on the relationship between social capital and job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth employees. There was a relationship between demographic characteristics (age/education) with organizational culture, social capital and job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth employees.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Job Burnout, Social Capital, Employees of Ministry of sports and Youth of Iran

1. INTRODUCTION

For any change and innovation in the organization, special attention should be paid to its organizational culture. Today, it is clear that different levels of organizational performance can be related to the type of organizational culture. Also, organizational culture can serve as a source for creating sustainable competitive advantages, because some cultures cannot be easily imitated by competitors (Hamzelouee et al., 2017). Organizational culture represents a set of values, beliefs, norms and understandings that the organization has in common with its employees (Greenberg, J., & Baron, 2001). Organizational culture creates a space for social interactions that these social interactions and face-to-face meetings lead to communication and trust; it is in such a space that social capital is formed (Brehm, J., & Wandy, 1997). Besides, it can be said that social capital is a resource that facilitates collective actions. Therefore, the more social capital is in people, the psychological pressure and various consequences such as increased transfers, absenteeism, etc. will decrease (Roxas, Banjo G. 2008). On the other hand, one of the important aspects of every person's life is his job. Job burnout is one of the most important job-related factors, especially in hard jobs. Job burnout is one of the psychological symptoms and it is mostly seen with jobs that are in contact with people for many hours (Khamarnia & Tourani, 2018). Job burnout is a psychological syndrome consisting of three axes: emotional exhaustion, reduced performance and depersonalization, and has complications such as: chronic fatigue, sleep disorders, various physical symptoms, negative and pessimistic tendencies towards colleagues and clients and feeling of guilt (Dimitrios & Konstantinos, 2014). Although burnout can occur in any job, it is a common global problem and epidemic in human service professions (o'brien, 2010). According to person-environment (PE) fit theory Organizational factors play an important role in the formation of job burnout. Job burnout in the long term causes psychological pressure for a person, so that one of the main causes of job burnout is the lack of fit and coordination between the person and his work environment (Lambert et al., 2020). In this regard, one of the areas that can lead to a poor fit between an individual and his work environment is organizational culture. Also, when organizations do not have enough knowledge of their organizational culture and its dimensions and indicators, they will face many problems in practice, such as organizational conflict, organizational incoherence and job burnout.

Therefore, identifying the organizational culture helps managers to use its strengths with full awareness and vision of the environment governing the organization and to predict the necessary measures for the weak points (Sargazi et al., 2019). Therefore, a favorable organizational culture can be a stimulus for productivity and increase the productivity of employees and reduce their job burnout. Dimitrios and Konstantinos (2014) stated that organizational culture strategy may be effective in reducing the level of stress and burnout by overcoming conflicts and requirements in the organization. Bennett et al.'s research (2000) has shown that there is an inverse and significant relationship between collaborative organizational culture and entrepreneurship with job burnout, or based on Lambert et al.'s (2010) results, job burnout is a negative response caused by the work environment and culture. Also, Sargazi et al. (2010) and Atai (2008) showed that there is a significant positive relationship between social capital and organizational culture. Therefore, since sports organizations, as a government organization, are the basic elements of every society, the survival, durability and progress of every society can depend on the quality and amount of support and its organizational culture and structure. Physical education and sports guide development and progress by having individual and collective missions. Therefore, by pursuing multiple goals in today's society, it plays a significant role in raising the quality of people's lives and their performance in sports fields.

It is necessary to take help from the principles and basics of sports management, and considering the importance of organizational culture and the relationship that the application of new strategies and changes in the structure of sports organizations has with organizational culture, it is appropriate to have a more complete and accurate understanding of organizational culture. Since the organizational culture can guide the employees of the physical training department of the province to their goals, and on the other hand, social capital is formed when people connect with each other in order to obtain resources and capital, in such a case, culture can act as a stimulus to facilitate and create these links between the members of the organization and can prevent employee burnout. Therefore, according to the above topics, the researcher is looking for the question that what is the relationship between organizational culture with social capital and job burnout among the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran?

2. METHODOLOGY

The research is an applied research in terms of purpose, and descriptive-correlation in terms of method. The research population was including of all the employees of the ministry of sports and youth of Iran (N=950).

Using the sampling table of Krejcie & Morgan 274 people were randomly selected as statistical sample. Based on this sample, 258 questionnaires were collected. The questionnaires used in this research were the standard organizational culture questionnaire of Denison et al (1999), job burnout by Hazel and Maslach (1977), social capital by Nahapiet and Ghoshal's (1998), and the validity of the questionnaire was confirmed by experts (10 people). To determine the reliability, the questionnaire was distributed among 15 people from the statistical population.

For the statistical analysis of the research findings, descriptive statistics were used to classify and describe the findings (mean, standard deviation, frequency distribution tables). In the inferential statistics section, the Kolmogorov Smirnov statistical test, one sample t test, analysis of variance, univariate and multiple regression, Pearson correlation coefficient and Sobel test were applied using SPSS 21.

3. FINDINGS

Main Hypothesis

There is relationship between organizational culture with social capital and job burnout of employees of ministry of sport and youth.

Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to test the hypothesis. According to the table, the significant level observed between the organizational culture of the employees of the ministry and the social capital is less than 0.05, as a result the hypothesis that declare: there is a significant relationship between the organizational culture and the social capital of the employees of the ministry, is approved.

But the significant level observed between the organizational culture of the employees and job burnout is more than 0.05, as a result, null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the organizational culture and the job burnout of employees is approved.

Table 1. Pearson correlation test results for organizational culture with social capital and job burnout of employees

		Job Burnout	Social Capital
Organizational Culture	r	-0/235	0/519
	p	0/228	<0/001

Hypothesis

There is a relationship between the dimensions of organizational culture and the social capital of the employees of the General Directorate of Sports and Youth in Tehran Province.

The hypothesis is approved. Also, according to the table, it can be seen that the correlation coefficient obtained between all the components is positive, in other words, there is a significant and direct relationship between the dimensions of organizational culture and the social capital of the employees of the ministry of sports and youth.

Table 2. The results of Pearson's correlation coefficient matrix between variables (dimensions of organizational culture and social capital)

		Participatory Culture	Compatibility culture	Adaptability culture	Missionary culture
Social Capital	r	0/54	0/55	0/576	0/519
	p	<0/001	<0/001	<0/001	<0/001

Hypothesis

There is relationship between the dimensions of organizational culture and the job burnout of the employees of the ministry of sports and youth.

The null hypothesis that there is no relationship between dimensions of organizational culture and job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth workers is confirmed.

Table 3. Pearson correlation coefficient matrix results between variables (dimensions of organizational culture and job burnout)

		Participatory Culture	Compatibility culture	Adaptability culture	Missionary culture
Job burnout	r	-0/098	-0/162	0/192	-0/235
	p	0/615	0/42	0/348	0/228

Hypothesis

Organizational culture can predict the social capital of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth.

To test this hypothesis, univariate regression test was used. The values ($F=14.15$ and $p=0.001$) show the existence of a linear relationship between the two variables. Also, according to the obtained results ($t=3.76$, $p=0.001$), the hypothesis that the organizational culture has a significant effect on the social capital of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth is confirmed.

Table 4. Regression table of the effect of organizational culture on social capital

Indicator	Not standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	R^2	t	p
	B	standard error	Beta			
Permanent	26/91	9/17		0/266	2/93	0/006
Organizational Culture	0/168	0/045	0/516		3/76	0/001

Hypothesis

Organizational culture can predict the job burnout of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth.

According to the results obtained from the table ($t=0.9$, $p=0.378$), the null hypothesis that there is no significant effect of organizational culture on job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth employees is confirmed.

Table 4. Regression table of the effect of organizational culture on job burnout

Indicator	Not standardized coefficients		standardized coefficients	t	p
	B	standard error	Beta		
Permanent	224/26	56/96		3/93	0/001
Job Burnout	-0/256	0/284	-0/198	-0/9	0/378

Hypothesis

Organizational culture has a significant mediating effect on the relationship between social capital and job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth employees.

To test the mediating effects in the proposed model and to determine their significance, Baron and Kenny's method and Sobel's test were used.

Table 5. Mediation analysis results to investigate the mediating role of organizational culture

Steps	predictor variable	Criterion variable	p	F	R ²	β	B
1	Social Capital	Organizational Culture	<0/001	16/85	0/28	0/374	0/238
2	Organizational Culture	Job Burnout	0/004	10/42	0/054	0/420	-0/269
3	Social Capital	Job Burnout	<0/001	76/3	0/35	0/589	0/553
4	Organizational Culture Social Capital	Job Burnout	0/098	44	0/285	0/677	0/108

The hypothesis that organizational culture has a significant mediating effect on the relationship between social capital and job burnout of Ministry of Sports and Youth employees is confirmed.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The inferential findings part of the results of the main hypotheses of the research based on the relationship between the research variables using regression and Pearson tests are as follows: there is a significant relationship between the organizational culture and the social capital of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran. ($r=0.519$, $p=0.001$) but there is no significant relationship between organizational culture and job burnout ($r=0.235$, $p=0.228$). There is a significant and direct relationship between the dimensions of organizational culture and the social capital of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran. There is no relationship between the dimensions of organizational culture and job burnout of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran. Also, the significant effect of organizational culture on the social capital of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran is confirmed ($t=3.76$, $p=0.001$), but the significant effect of organizational culture on the job burnout of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran is not confirmed. ($t=-0.9$, $p=0.378$) Also, organizational culture has a significant mediating effect on the relationship between social capital and job burnout of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran. Also, there is no relationship between demographic characteristics (age/education) with organizational culture, social capital and job burnout of employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran. There is a relationship between organizational culture and social capital and job burnout of employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to test the hypothesis. According to the significant level observed between the organizational culture of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran and the social capital, there is a significant relationship between the organizational culture and the social capital of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran. But according to the significant level observed between the organizational culture of the employees of the Ministry of Sports and Youth of Iran and job burnout, there is no significant relationship between the organizational culture and job burnout of the employees of the Ministry. The results are consistent with the findings of Taghizadeh (2010), Sargazi et al. (2010), Atai (2018), Ondracek (2011), Zhang and Ziadoudi (2009), Dijk et al. (2003), all of which emphasize the significant relationship between organizational culture and social capital. Taghizadeh (2013) in the study of the relationship between organizational culture and social capital of teachers in Shiraz boys' high schools showed that there is a significant relationship between organizational culture and social capital. Atai (2008) showed that there is a significant relationship between social capital and organizational culture and the component of cooperation and mutual cooperation got the highest rank. Zhang and Ziadoudi (2009) indicated that organizational culture has a positive effect on social capital. Dijk et al. (2002) in the research entitled organizational culture, unity capabilities and social capital, showed that the amount of social capital that each company creates and maintains and the use of company resources depends on the company's integration capabilities, which in turn affects the characteristics Internal factors are especially dependent on organizational culture. Social capital is one of the most important indicators of the growth and development of any society. Therefore, the subject of social capital is considered as a basic principle to achieve sustainable development and should provide the necessary tools to improve and strengthen social capital. Therefore, the subject of social capital is considered the main axis of management of organizations and those managers who can achieve more production and development of social capital in relation to the society are called successful. Culture is an

asset because shared beliefs lead to ease of communication. It also leads to the creation of an attitude of coordination, commitment and capital, and in this case, it leads to better performance and effectiveness in the organization. But despite this, a strong culture may lead to an increase in efficiency in terms of resource utilization and at the same time be ineffective, because the beliefs and values do not conform to the needs of the organization, members and other founders, and as a result, it becomes a liability. Therefore, the nature and content of values is the main factor in the effect of culture on the effectiveness of the organization. Due to the significant relationship between organizational culture and social capital, the knowledge of organizational culture is extremely important for the managers of the Ministry of Sports and Youth, and the culture that governs the organization reflects the way of life of the organization.

It is in the shadow of the culture that dominates the organization that people work, and according to the dynamics of the environment, transformation and change in organizations seem necessary. Therefore, for any change and innovation in the organization, special attention should be paid to organizational culture. Organizational culture management can play a major role in the development of human resources and improvement of work behavior and social capital, and even according to various researches, it can reduce job burnout. Thus, special attention should be paid to the investigation of the role of management in organizational culture and its position on job stressors and job satisfaction on the one hand and organizational commitment and social capital on the other hand. When organizations do not have enough knowledge of their organizational culture and its dimensions and indicators, they will face many problems in practice, such as organizational conflict, lack of organizational cohesion, and reduced performance, job burnout. Therefore, a favorable organizational culture can be a stimulus for productivity and increase the productivity of employees and reduce their job burnout.

REFERENCE LIST

- Allameh, M & et al (2011), The relationship between Organizational Culture and Knowledge Management. *Procardia Computer Science*, Vol.3, PP: 1224- 1236.
- Anthony J. Cedoline. (2000), *Experts from job burnout in public education; symptoms cause and survival skills*; published by the teacher's college Columbia university.
- Antonsen, Stain (2009) "The relationship between culture and safety of offshore supply vessels". *Safety science*, Vol.47, No.8, PP: 1118-1128.
- Bent, M. & et al (2000) Effect of cognitive-behavioral treatments to PTSD an anger. In *social issue: Pottraumatic Stress*.17, 113-131.
- Beugclsdijk, S & Kcan, C (2009) "A dyadic approach to the impact of differences in organizational culture on relationship performance". *Industrial Marketing Management*, Vol.38, No.3, PP; 312-323.
- Boyas j, Wind, I, L (2010), Employment-based social capital, job stress, and employee burnout: A public child welfare employee structural model, *Children and Youth Services Review*, pp. 380–388
- Boyas j, Wind, I, L Kang s,y (2012), Exploring the relationship between employment-based social capital, job stress, burnout, and intent to leave among child protection workers: An age-based path analysis model, *Children and out Services Review*, volume 34, pp,50-62
- Burt, R. S. (2000) "The network structure of social capital" *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 22. capital and Employment Practices"; *Academy of management Review*.
- Ching-Fu Chen and Shu-Chuan Chen (2012). Burnout and Work Engagement Among Cabin Crew: Antecedents and Consequences, *The International Journal of Aviation Psychology*, 22:1, 41-58.
- Cohen, D. & I. prusak. (2001). *In good company-how social capital makes organizations work*, Harvard business school press, Boston, Massachusetts.
- Cohen, D. & I. prusak. (2001). *In good company-how social capital makes organizations work*, Harvard business school press, Boston, Massachusetts.
- Coleman, J. S. (1990). Social capital in the creation of human capital. *American Journal of Sociology*, 94, 95-120.
- Coleman, J. S. and Hoffer, T. (1987) *Public and Private Schools: the impact of communities*, Basic Books, New York.
- Colman, J.S. (1990). *Foundations of social theory*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard university press.
- Cox, T. stress, fourth edition, *British cataloging in publication data* ,1988
- Denison, D (2000) "Organizational culture: can it be a key lever for driving I organizational change?".

International institute for management development.

- Delong, D. W and Fahey, (2000) "Diagnostic culture barriers to knowledge I management". Academy of management executive. Vol. 14, No.4.
- Denison. D. (2005). [http://www. Denison culture. Com/culture/ culture Link/Html](http://www.Denison.com/culture/cultureLink/Html).
- Dijk, H. (2002). "Organizational Culture and its Impact on Organizational Effectiveness in Management Faculty Staff", [Thesis]. Tehran: Shahid Beheshti University.
- DIMITRIOS, B and KONSTANTINOS, V (2014) "ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND JOB BURNOUT – A REVIEW", *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in*, 2321-886X; ISSN(P): 2347-4572, Vol. 2, Issue 1, Jan 2014, 43-62
- Ghafornyan(2012).the relationship among organizational culture and entrepreneurship in personal of azad university islamshahrj.educ.manage.stud.2(3)55-60 92015.
- Greenberg, J., & Baron, R. A. (2001). *Behavior in Organizations*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Lambert E, Hogan NL, Jiang S. A preliminary examination of the relationship between organizational structure and emotional burnout among correctional staff. *The Howard journal of Criminal Justice*, 2010. 49 (2) pp. 125-146
- Marlow, L. and Hierimeil, R. (1987). *The teaching profession: who stays and who leaves?* (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 315 380).
- Maslach C, and Goldenberg J. Prevention of burnout: new perspectives. *Apple Prevent Psycho* 1988; 7: 63-74.
- Mosaybian, N and Jafari, M. (2014). The study of relationship between job security and organizational commitment, *ter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review* Vol. Kuwait Chap 3, No.6(a); Feb.
- O'brien, L Janice, (2010)," structural empowerment, psychological empowerment, and burnout in registered staff nurses working in outpatient dialysis centers "a dissertation submitted to the graduate school-newarkrutgers, the state university of new jersey in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of doctor of philosophy graduate program in nursing.
- Proosser, S. (2006), The measurement of experience burnout, *Research quarterly for exercise and sport* Volume 44, pp(55-66).synthesis', *Review of Educational Research*, 72, i, 31-60
- Putnam, R. (2000). *Bowling alone: the collapse and revival of American community*, New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Putnam, R. (2000). *Bowling alone: the collapse and revival of American community*, New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Putnam, Robert D. (ED), (2002), "Democracies in flux, the evolution of social capital in contemporary society", Oxford University Press.
- Riggle, R. J., Edmondson, D. R., & Hansen, J. D. (2009). A meta-analysis of the relationship between perceived organizational support and job outcomes: 20 years of research. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(10), 1027-1030.
- Robbins, Stephen P. (2005), *Essential of Organizational Behavior*, eighth edition, Prentice. Hall.
- Robinson D. (2000). Coaching tip: self-efficacy the key to the client confidence graduate works in social physiology, vol,12, p124.
- Roxas, Banjo G. (2008). social capital for knowledge management: the case of small and medium- size enterprise in the Asia pacific region. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 13, No. 2, 57–77.
- Sargazi, Hosseinali, et al. (2010). The effect of social capital on organizational culture in Iran's governmental and non-governmental higher education centers (case study: Golestan Province), *Cultural sociology*, 2(1).